

Complete Genome Sequence of *Enterobacter* Phage vB_EcRAM-01, a New *Pseudotevenvirus* against the *Enterobacter cloacae* Complex

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ABSTRACT Here, we present the complete genome sequence of *Enterobacter* phage vB_EcRAM-01, isolated from waters of the Río Abajo river, in Panama City, Panama. This phage has deployed lytic activity against the *Enterobacter cloacae* complex, a pathogen of clinical importance in intensive care units. It belongs to the *Myoviridae* family and has a double-stranded DNA genome that is 178,477 bp long and contains 293 open reading frames (ORFs).

The *Enterobacter cloacae* complex has been classified by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a priority for antimicrobial research and development (1). In intensive care units, phage therapy has become a viable option for treating multidrug-resistant bacteria, among which *E. cloacae* represents a serious threat (2, 3).

The *Enterobacter* phage vB_EcRAM-01 was isolated from waters of the Río Abajo river in Panama City, Panama (coordinates, 9°00'55.2"N 79°29'25.6"W), using *E. cloacae* strain ATCC 23355 as a propagation host, which was grown previously in tryptic soy broth at 37°C for 24 h (4, 5). Phage isolation, propagation, and purification were performed using the soft-agar overlay method (6). DNA extraction was performed using the QIAamp MinElute virus spin kit (Qiagen, Valencia, CA, USA), according to the manufacturer's instructions. The DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT DNA library preparation kit (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) through tagmentation, PCR amplification, PCR cleanup, and library normalization. Genome sequencing was performed with the Illumina MiSeq platform (2 × 250-bp paired-end protocol, 300 cycles). Raw reads (629,372 reads in total) were checked for quality using FastQC (www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc) and trimmed using Trimmomatic v0.39 (7). The genome was assembled through SPAdes v3.15.1 (8), resulting in a single contig with 8.96-fold coverage. We mapped the reads against the resulting contig to confirm sequence ends using Bowtie (9). Alignments with closely related phages showed the presence of the same annotated features which indicates this single contig represents the complete genome. The genome was initially annotated with the fast annotation algorithm using RASTk v2.0 subsystem technology (10–12). The putative open reading frames (ORFs) were verified using GeneMarkS v4.28 (13, 14) and Glimmer v3.02 (15, 16).

The ORF functions were annotated using the protein basic local alignment search tool (blastp) of the NCBI server (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) based on a search of the nonredundant protein sequence database (17), HHpred using the structural/domain

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database (<https://toolkit.tuebingen.mpg.de/tools/hhpred>) (18, 19), and HMMER v2.41.1 through the HMM database (20, 21).

vB_EcRAM-01 has a 178,477-bp genome containing 293 genes, of which 86 have a predicted function associated with morphology, inactivation, cell adsorption, DNA injection, and host lysis. No resistance (ResFinder 4.1, <https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/>) (22–24), virulence (VirulenceFinder 2.0, <https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/VirulenceFinder/>) (25, 26), or allergenicity-related (AllergenOnline, <http://www.allergenonline.org/databasefasta.shtml>) (27) genes were identified. The raw reads were assembled, automatically annotated, and manually curated. This genome codes for 2 tRNAs, namely, a tRNA-Met (cat) and a tRNA-Gly (tcc). *Enterobacter* phage vB_EcRAM-01 is most closely related to *Cronobacter* phage vB_CsaM_1eE (GenBank accession number [NC_048646.1](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/NC_048646.1)) with 90.11% nucleotide sequence identity determined by pyani v0.2.11 (28). Therefore, *Enterobacter* phage vB_EcRAM-01 is a new member of the *Pseudotevenvirus* genus within the *Tevenvirinae* subfamily and *Myoviridae* family, according to the genus demarcation criteria (>70% nucleotide identity over the full genome length) recommended by the ICTV Bacterial and Archaeal Viruses Subcommittee (29).

vB_EcRAM-01 exhibited specific litic activity against 19 clinical *E. cloacae* isolates.

The complete annotation of the vB_EcRAM-01 genome can be found in the GenBank database (30).

Data availability. The complete sequence of *Enterobacter* phage vB_EcRAM-01 has been deposited in GenBank under accession number [OL551674](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/OL551674) and BioSample accession [SAMN23426491](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN23426491). Raw data can be accessed through SRA number [SRR18344380](https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR18344380).

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REFERENCES

1. WHO. 2017. Global priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria to guide research, discovery, and development of new antibiotics. WHO, Geneva, Switzerland.
2. Abedon ST. 2017. Information phage therapy research should report. *Pharmaceuticals* 10:43. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph10020043>.
3. Abedon ST (ed). 2008. Bacteriophage ecology: population growth, evolution, and impact of bacterial viruses, 1 ed. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, England.
4. Gaviña AG, González de SM, Castaño OJ. 2012. Técnica para aislamiento de bacteriófagos específicos para *E. coli* DH5 α a partir de aguas residuales. *Rev MVZ Córdoba* 17:2852–2860. <https://doi.org/10.21897/rmvz.253>.
5. Meza A. 2016. Aislamiento y caracterización de bacteriófagos para cepas nosocomiales DE *Acinetobacter baumannii* de Lima e Iquitos, Perú 2014–2015. Universidad Católica De Santa María, Lima, Peru.
6. Piuri M. 2019. Los bacteriófagos: del genoma al metagenoma. Departamento de Química Biológica Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina.
7. Bolger AM, Lohse M, Usadel B. 2014. Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30:2114–2120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>.
8. Bankevich A, Nurk S, Antipov D, Gurevich AA, Dvorkin M, Kulikov AS, Lesin VM, Nikolenko SI, Pham S, Prjibelski AD, Pyshkin AV, Sirotkin AV, Vyahhi N, Tesler G, Alekseyev MA, Pevzner PA. 2012. SPAdes: a new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *J Comput Biol* 19:455–477. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cmb.2012.0021>.
9. Langmead B, Trapnell C, Pop M, Salzberg SL. 2009. Ultrafast and memory-efficient alignment of short DNA sequences to the human genome. *Genome Biol* 10:R25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/gb-2009-10-3-r25>.
10. Brettin T, Davis JJ, Disz T, Edwards RA, Gerdes S, Olsen GJ, Olson R, Overbeek R, Parrello B, Pusch GD, Shukla M, Thomason JA, Stevens R, Vonstein V, Wattam AR, Xia F. 2015. RASTtk: a modular and extensible implementation of the RAST algorithm for building custom annotation pipelines and annotating batches of genomes. *Sci Rep* 5:8365. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep08365>.
11. Overbeek R, Olson R, Pusch GD, Olsen GJ, Davis JJ, Disz T, Edwards RA, Gerdes S, Parrello B, Shukla M, Vonstein V, Wattam AR, Xia F, Stevens R. 2014. The SEED and the Rapid Annotation of microbial genomes using Subsystems Technology (RAST). *Nucleic Acids Res* 42:D206–D214. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkt1226>.
12. Aziz RK, Bartels D, Best AA, DeJongh M, Disz T, Edwards RA, Formosa K, Gerdes S, Glass EM, Kubal M, Meyer F, Olsen GJ, Olson R, Osterman AL, Overbeek RA, McNeil LK, Paarmann D, Paczian T, Parrello B, Pusch GD, Reich C, Stevens R, Vassieva O, Vonstein V, Wilke A, Zagnitko O. 2008. The RAST server: Rapid Annotations using Subsystems Technology. *BMC Genomics* 9:75. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-9-75>.
13. Delcher AL, Bratke KA, Powers EC, Salzberg SL. 2007. Identifying bacterial genes and endosymbiont DNA with Glimmer. *Bioinformatics* 23:673–679. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btm009>.
14. Salzberg SL, Delcher AL, Kasif S, White O. 1998. Microbial gene identification using interpolated Markov models. *Nucleic Acids Res* 26:544–548. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/26.2.544>.
15. Besemer J, Borodovsky M. 2005. GeneMark: Web software for gene finding in

- prokaryotes, eukaryotes and viruses. *Nucleic Acids Res* 33:W451–W454. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gki487>.
16. Besemer J, Lomsadze A, Borodovsky M. 2001. GeneMarkS: a self-training method for prediction of gene starts in microbial genomes. Implications for finding sequence motifs in regulatory regions. *Nucleic Acids Res* 29: 2607–2618. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/29.12.2607>.
 17. Altschul SF, Madden TL, Schäffer AA, Zhang J, Zhang Z, Miller W, Lipman DJ. 1997. Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database search programs. *Nucleic Acids Res* 25:3389–3402. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/25.17.3389>.
 18. Zimmermann L, Stephens A, Nam S-Z, Rau D, Kübler J, Lozajic M, Gabler F, Söding J, Lupas AN, Alva V. 2018. A completely reimplemented MPI bioinformatics toolkit with a new HHpred server at its core. *J Mol Biol* 430: 2237–2243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2017.12.007>.
 19. Hildebrand A, Remmert M, Biegert A, Söding J. 2009. Fast and accurate automatic structure prediction with HHpred. *Proteins* 77:128–132. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.22499>.
 20. Potter SC, Luciani A, Eddy SR, Park Y, Lopez R, Finn RD. 2018. HMMER Web server: 2018 update. *Nucleic Acids Res* 46:W200–W204. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky448>.
 21. Finn RD, Clements J, Eddy SR. 2011. HMMER Web server: interactive sequence similarity searching. *Nucleic Acids Res* 39:W29–W37. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr367>.
 22. Bortolaia V, Kaas RS, Ruppe E, Roberts MC, Schwarz S, Cattoir V, Philippon A, Allesoe RL, Rebelo AR, Florensa AF, Fagelhauer L, Chakraborty T, Neumann B, Werner G, Bender JK, Stingl K, Nguyen M, Coppens J, Xavier BB, Malhotra-Kumar S, Westh H, Pinholt M, Anjum MF, Duggett NA, Kempf I, Nykäsenoja S, Olkkola S, Wiczorek K, Amaro A, Clemente L, Mossong J, Losch S, Ragimbeau C, Lund O, Aarestrup FM. 2020. ResFinder 4.0 for predictions of phenotypes from genotypes. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 75:3491–3500. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa345>.
 23. Zankari E, Allesøe R, Joensen KG, Cavaco LM, Lund O, Aarestrup FM. 2017. PointFinder: a novel web tool for WGS-based detection of antimicrobial resistance associated with chromosomal point mutations in bacterial pathogens. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 72:2764–2768. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkx217>.
 24. Camacho C, Coulouris G, Avagyan V, Ma N, Papadopoulos J, Bealer K, Madden TL. 2009. BLAST+: architecture and applications. *BMC Bioinformatics* 10:421. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-10-421>.
 25. Joensen KG, Scheutz F, Lund O, Hasman H, Kaas RS, Nielsen EM, Aarestrup FM. 2014. Real-time whole-genome sequencing for routine typing, surveillance, and outbreak detection of verotoxigenic *Escherichia coli*. *J Clin Microbiol* 52:1501–1510. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.03617-13>.
 26. Malberg Tetzschner AM, Johnson JR, Johnston BD, Lund O, Scheutz F. 2020. In silico genotyping of *Escherichia coli* isolates for extraintestinal virulence genes by use of whole-genome sequencing data. *J Clin Microbiol* 58:e01269-20. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.01269-20>.
 27. Goodman RE, Ebisawa M, Ferreira F, Sampson HA, van Ree R, Vieths S, Baumert JL, Bohle B, Lalithambika S, Wise J, Taylor SL. 2016. AllergenOnline: a peer-reviewed, curated allergen database to assess novel food proteins for potential cross-reactivity. *Mol Nutr Food Res* 60:1183–1198. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201500769>.
 28. Pritchard L, H Glover R, Humphris S, G Elphinstone J, K Toth I. 2016. Genomics and taxonomy in diagnostics for food security: soft-rotting enterobacterial plant pathogens. *Anal Methods* 8:12–24. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5AY02550H>.
 29. Turner D, Kropinski AM, Adriaenssens EM. 2021. A roadmap for genome-based phage taxonomy. *Viruses* 13:506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v13030506>.
 30. Karsch-Mizrachi I, Nakamura Y, Cochrane G, International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration. 2012. The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Res* 40:D33–D37. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr1006>.